

MEASUREMENT AND SIMULATION OF EDGE DEFECTS IN TURNING OF SiCp/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a three-dimensional finite element simulation along with an experimental method were carried out to study the edge defects in turning of SiCp/Al composites. The formation process of edge defects near the exit of turning was analyzed, and the effects of cutting depth, feed rate and spindle speed on the sizes of edge defects were investigated. The results indicate that a negative deformation plane begins to form as the tool approaches the end of the cut and the crack propagation along the negative deformation plane results in the edge defects. In addition, the size of edge defects increases with the increase of cutting depth and feed rate, and the spindle speed has little influence on the size of edge defects. The numerical results were also compared to the turning experimental data and found to be in reasonable agreement.

1 INTRODUCTION

SiC particle reinforced Al matrix (SiCp/Al) composites exhibit excellent physical and mechanical properties compared with conventional materials, such as high specific modulus, improved resistance to wear, low coefficient of thermal expansion and high thermal conductivity [1-3]. In the last decades, SiCp/Al composites have been used in aerospace structures, turbine engine blades, electronic packaging, satellite bearing, laser reflector and so on [4-5]. However, due to the addition of the rigid ceramic particles, the machining of SiCp/Al composites are very difficult and the good surface precision and high edge quality are difficult to guarantee. In a broader sense, the edge defects of this kind is defined as an undesirable effect generated at the edge of a workpiece after the machining process. The edge defects not only has a negative effect on the dimensional precision of the parts, but also leads to the failure of SiCp/Al composites in the service process.

It is well known that cutting parameters, workpiece material, tool material and geometries as well as cooling conditions are all factors that affect the machined surface integrity. In the past, there have been lots of investigations on the machining of SiCp/Al composites, dealing with tool wear, surface quality and chip formation. Sahin et al. [6-7] and Antoniomaria et al. [8] have investigated the effect of tool material on the tool wear behaviour when machining SiCp/Al composites at different cutting conditions and found that the tool life decreased considerably with increasing particle size and cutting speed. Several researchers [9-11] have investigated the effect of tool material and cutting parameters on surface roughness when turning SiCp/Al composites and concluded that higher cutting speeds and lower feed rates produced better surface quality and the surface finish was much better when SiC particles were removed by pressed into or cut through mechanisms. Dabade et al. [12] have studied the chip formation mechanism during machining of Al/SiCp composites and shown that not only the cutting speed, but also the feed rate has a significant effect on the chip segment. Moreover, the burr formation and delamination in machining ductile material and fiber-reinforced composites have been reported. Chern [13-14] has analyzed the mechanism of burr formation and edge breakout in metal cutting, and proposed a burr formation/breakout model for orthogonal cutting. The 2D and 3D oblique cutting were conducted by Sung-Lim Ko et al. [15] and Hashimura et al. [16], respectively, and it is found that the burr size or fracture location decreases as the inclination angle increases. In addition, there are some researches have investigated the effects of drilling parameters on the delamination characteristics on the entry and exit side of the hole in drilling of fiber-reinforced composites [17-21].

However, up to now, little research has yet comprehensively demonstrated the edge quality and the influencing factors when turning of SiCp/Al composites.

In this paper, in order to study the formation mechanism of the edge defects in turning of SiCp/Al composites, a three dimension homogeneous finite element model was established by using commercial software (ABAQUS/Explicit). The model is then experimentally evaluated with a polycrystal diamond tool, and the effects of cutting depth, feed rate and spindle speed on the size of edge defects were analyzed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

SiCp/Al composites were fabricated by powder metallurgy method, which were produced in the Institute of Metal Research, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Shenyang. Fig.1 shows the microstructure of 30 vol. % SiCp/Al composites, and it can be observed that the SiC particles are polyhedral with many sharp corners and average edge size of about 10 μm , which are homogeneously distributed in the microstructure.

The experimental setup is schematically illustrated in Fig. 2, and the diameter and length of the cylindrical specimen are 150 mm and 200 mm, respectively. In order to obtain the edge quality under different cutting parameters, a number of grooves with 3 mm in width and 6 mm in depth were machined, as shown in Fig.2. All the cutting tests were performed on a horizontal lathe J1MK460, and the summary of experimental conditions is listed in Table 1. The turning tests were performed with polycrystal diamond (PCD) tool, and the PCD insert has the grain size of 25 μm . The tool rake angle is $\gamma_0 = 0^\circ$, the clearance angle is 8° , and the inclination angle is $\lambda_s = 10^\circ$. During experiments, only one of the parameters, such as the cutting depth was varied while the feed rate and spindle speed were held constants to observe the effect of individual parameter on the exit edge defects. After testing, the fracture morphology and the size of edge defects were viewed by a digital optical microscope (KEYENCE, VHX-1000).

Fig. 1 Microstructure of SiCp/Al composites Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of turning experimental system.

Table 1 Summary of experimental conditions.

Machine	J1MK460 horizontal lathe
Tool	Polycrystal diamond (PCD) tool, grain size, 25 μm , rake angle, 0° , clearance angle, 8° , inclination angle, 10°
Workpiece materials	30 vol.% SiCp/Al composites
Cutting depth (mm)	1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3
Feed rate (mm/r)	0.135, 0.237, 0.32, 0.41, 0.54
Spindle speed (r/min)	160, 240, 350, 500, 720
Cutting conditions	Dry

3. FINITE ELEMENT MODELING PROCEDURE

A three-dimensional finite element model has been established by using ABAQUS/CAE module to simulate the turning process, as shown in Fig. 3. The workpiece dimension was 2×1×1 mm. The arc radius of the tool tip is 0.01 mm. The simulation cutting parameters are the same as that of the experiment. In order to accurately predict the edge defects, finer mesh was maintained in the regions of deformation zone by defining a high mesh density to cover the entire chip, the tool-chip contact area, and the cut-out area, and low mesh density to cover the other area of the workpiece. The units of the modeling process were: mm, MPa, N, s, mm/s.

The tool was polycrystalline diamond (PCD) cutter which was defined as a rigid body for the sake of reducing the computational time. The workpiece material was modeled as elastic-plastic with isotropic strain hardening. The material properties of SiCp/Al composites and PCD tool were listed in Table 2, and the specific data of the plastic phase constitutive relation of the SiCp/Al composites were listed in Table 3.

In this study, the physical chip separation criterion available with ABAQUS/Explicite was employed, which was based on the equivalent plastic strain, ϵ . When an element reaches the damage plastic strain value, ϵ_d , the damage parameter D in Eq. 1 equals to one. When this occurs, the material fails, and the corresponding element will be deleted.

$$D = \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_d} = 1 \quad (1)$$

Three-dimensional, eight-node thermal coupling hexahedron element featuring reduced integration (C3D8RT) was used to define the workpiece, and three-dimensional tetrahedron element (C3D4T) was used to define the tool. The workpiece was constrained against movement in any direction, and the cutting tool was given a predetermined speed along the cutting direction and feed directions, respectively.

Fig. 3 Finite element model of SiCp/Al composites

Table 2 Material properties of SiCp/Al composites and PCD tool [22-23]

Material parameters	PCD tools	SiCp/Al composites
ρ , density (kg/m ³)	3520	2940
E, Young's modulus (GPa)	1147	258
ν , Poisson's ratio	0.07	0.2
κ , thermal conductivity (W/m K)	2100	235
C_p , specific heat (J/kg K)	525	850

Table 3 Plastic stress-strain relationship of SiCp/Al composite

Stress(MPa)	Strain($\times 10^{-4}$)
220	0
260	0.0014
290	0.0022
330	0.0029
400	0.0036
460	0.0042

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 FORMATION MECHANISM OF EDGE DEFECTS

The objective of finite element analysis is to study the formation mechanism of edge defects, so as to provide a theoretical foundation to improve the edge quality as possible as we can. According to the distribution of the stress field and the variation of the chip geometry characteristic, eight stages have been divided for the process of the edge defects formation, and they can explain the process very well. The first stage is the initial contact stage between the chip and tool when the tool cut into workpiece which is shown in Fig. 4a, it describes continuous cutting with shear type chip for brittle materials, and the shear zone can be seen obviously, Φ is the shear angle, T_0 is the undeformed chip thickness. As the tool moving, the elastic deformation zone appears at the workpiece edge due to the elastic bending, and the plastic deformation zone around the shear zone is also considered to be extended toward the edge, as shown in Fig. 4b. Fig. 4c shows the plastic deformation zone has reached the workpiece edge, and the plastic deformation zone near the shear zone continues to extend and it is going to connect with plastic zone around the edge. Fig. 4d shows the critical transition stage: there is a zone in the cutting layer and it is defined as the stress transfer zone, and the distance from the tool tip point A to the workpiece end surface is defined as the critical transition distance ω . The stress transfer zone can pass on the maximum stress to the workpiece edge below the cutting path and hinder the chip formation. Fig. 4e shows the flexure deformation stage, and an obvious flexure deformation occurs at the pivot point O due to the effect of the cutting force. The concentrated stress zone below the cutting path is called the negative shear zone, and ψ is defined as the negative shear angle. Fig. 4f shows the crack initiation stage: the crack source occurs at the tool tip when the concentrated stress value exceeds the material tensile strength, and it is caused by the material internal dislocation, it initiates in the negative shear zone and will grow toward the pivot point O. Fig. 4g shows the crack propagation stage: the crack propagates along the direction of the negative shear angle. Additionally, a mixed mode crack occurs in the negative shear zone, and both the opening mode crack and the sliding mode crack are existed. The workpiece edge also deforms slightly due to crack propagation. The fracture separation stage is shown in Fig. 4h, in this stage, as the tool approaching the workpiece end and continuous crack propagation, the edge material separate from the workpiece under the tool moving, eventually, the edge defect formation. The main parameters of the edge defect are the height H and the length L which are also shown in Fig. 4h. Therefore, the main reason of the edge defect formation is that the crack source appears at the tool tip because of the dislocation pile when the tool approaches to the workpiece end. Furthermore, when the crack propagates in the material interior, the energy need to be released to form a new surface, and the crack begins to extend when it reaches a critical value. So the negative shear angle and the chip formation are the bases of the edge defect formation.

Fig. 4 Process of the edge defects formation

4.2 EDGE DEFECTS

For studying the morphology and size of the edge defects, all the machined components were cut in

a wire electrical discharge machine. When the feed rate and spindle speed are 0.237mm/r and 500r/min, respectively, the exit edge defect morphology under five different cutting depths is displayed in Fig. 5. Figs. 5a, c, e, g, i are the morphology of the edge defects in the length direction, while Figs. 5b, d, f, h, j are the morphology of the edge defects in the height direction. From the figure, it can be observed that brittle fractures are very clear, and the fracture surface is very rough due to the high volume fraction of SiC particle in the composites. With the increase of the cutting depth, the values of length and height increase significantly.

Fig. 5 Edge morphology on the exit surface, at cutting depth of: (a) and (b) 1 mm, (c) and (d) 1.5 mm, (e) and (f) 2 mm, (g) and (h) 2.5 mm, (i) and (j) 3 mm.

4.3 INFLUENCE OF CUTTING PARAMETERS ON THE SIZES OF EDGE DEFECTS

Fig. 6 shows the variation of the edge defect size with the change of cutting depth, feed rate and spindle speed. Fig. 6a shows the effect of the cutting depth on the edge defect size when the spindle speed and feed rate are 500 r/min and 0.237mm/r, respectively. It can be seen that the edge defect length and height increase as the cutting depth increases. The values of edge defect size increased slowly when the cutting depth was less than 2.5 mm. With continuous increase of cutting depth, the size of edge defects increased very quickly. The reason is that with the increasing of cutting depth, the higher cutting force will induce the cutting action that tends to be more unstable during machining, which increases the exit edge defects size. In addition, when the cutting depth and spindle speed are kept constant, the effect of the feed rate on the edge defect size is shown in Fig. 6b. From the figure, it can be noted that with the increase of the feed rate, the size of exit edge defects increases significantly, and the dependence of edge defect sizes on feed rate appeared to be linear relationship. Fig. 6c presents the effect of spindle speed on the size of exit edge defects, and it can be seen that the spindle speed has little effect on the size of exit edge defects. The reason is because the high volume fraction of SiC particles in this material, the effect of Al alloy matrix softening is not obvious. Similar observations were reported in [9-10] for machining of SiCp/6061Al composites under different cutting parameters. Therefore, in order obtain a fine edge quality and precise machining accuracy, a smaller cutting depth and feed rate must be used in turning of SiCp/Al composites; on the contrary, the spindle speed can be adopted as high as possible.

From Figs. 6a, b and c, it is worth noting that there are some similar phenomena: the simulated curves (dashed curves) are smoother than the experimental curves (solid curves), and the simulated

values are smaller than the experimental values. These can be explained by the present simulation model. In this study, the material is assumed to homogeneous isotropic, and has no defects. In fact, besides the tool wear and machine vibration, the defects in the real material could cause the larger edge defect size obtained from the experiments than that in the calculation.

Fig. 6 Influence of cutting parameters on edge defects sizes, (a) cutting depth, (b) feed rate and (c) spindle speed.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A 3D finite element model and experiment were carried out to study the formation mechanism of edge defects and the effects of the cutting parameters on sizes of edge defects during turning of SiCp/Al composites with PCD tools. Good agreement of the results was found between the experimental and calculated. The following conclusions can be drawn:

According to the process of the edge defect formation, it is found that a negative deformation plane begins to form as the tool approaches to the end of the cut, and the crack initiation and propagation along the negative deformation plane results in the edge defects.

From the experiment and calculation results, it can be concluded that the edge defect size almost linearly increases with increasing cutting depth and feed rate, while spindle speed has little effect on the sizes of edge defects. Therefore, in order obtain a fine edge quality during turning of SiCp/Al composites, spindle speed should be as high as possible, but not the cutting depth and feed rate.

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